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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 6

Pages: 594-601

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1986

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12606794

Manuscript Accepted: 05-30-2024

Analyzing and Unraveling Man's Source of Worth and Identity through Utterances in Selected Modern Hymns

Jethro James V. Achivida*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Literature is a medium of expressing what it is to be human and to feel human, and religious texts are one category of these expressions of humanity. Christian hymns mirror the right beliefs and right practices of their faiths. As such, this study analyzed where man roots and finds his source of worth and identity through selected contemporary hymns. The hymn “My Worth is not in what I own” and “I’d rather have Jesus” were selected using deliberate sampling. The paper utilized a descriptive qualitative design, and subjected the two hymns to both document analysis and thematic analysis, where several observations and interpretations have emerged. Based on the interpreted data, linguistic features show the dominance of the first-person pronouns and negation as effective devices in pointing the meaning and source of worth and identity. Literary devices such as comparison and rhyme also affect the rhythm and understanding of the hymns toward the discovery of one’s identity and worth. The Searlean assertive, declarative, and expressive acts are found to be evident in the formation and discovery of one’s worth and identity, in that there is assertion, redirection, and response to the newfound/expounded identity and worth. In conclusion, this study provides compelling evidence that material pursuits of the speaker in the two hymns are in no match and comparison to the grander scale of Jesus as ultimate source of identity, worth, pleasure and treasure. These findings have important implications that hymns do not only lay out spiritual and theological truths, but also individual and psycho-social aspects of meaning making of what it is to exist, what it is to be human, and why we exist. As such, this study contributes to our understanding of hymns. Overall, this research highlights the significance of analysis of hymns and suggests potential avenues for future investigation.

Keywords: *hymns, literary criticism, stylistics, document analysis, formalist, New Criticism Theory*

Introduction

Literature breathes and speaks expressions and elements of humanity. Where there is literature, a portion of oneself is being represented, if not imitated. Literary works then often show these types of realities, whether contrived or lived. It is also said that literature shows identity, whether of a collective kind or an individual type. Literature, as a means of portrayal of what it is to be human, encapsulates the essence of artistry that allows others to connect and relate to the masterpieces produced across various time periods.

Poetry has proven itself to be a powerful agent in the expression of one’s self. Through linguistic, literary, and cultural expression, poetry has championed the universality of these realities and real expressions. The place of poetry is rooted and founded in the pages of history and books and the memory of man. Poems have relayed the thoughts of the period, the “spirit of the age”, the mind of the poet, the intended emotion the poet wishes to convey, and the power of words in both order and chaos. Man savours and enjoys poetry to look better and deeper into his existence and ponder on realities he faces, observes, and encounters. Hymns are art of twofold creativity: music and poetry. As per Nnamdi-Eruchalu and Nwude (2022), Christian hymns are associated with the Christian faith, its core beliefs, its practices, and its philosophies. Theological truths are at the core of every hymn. And such hymns have twofold goals: a God-directed goal of worship and adoration and a human-directed goal of edification, encouragement, motivation, and affecting of the soul and heart. This paper will focus on the poetic side of hymns, as types of literary works. Hymns are known for its established meter, rhyme schemes, and several formats. If one is to consider the nature of hymns like how Dante Alighieri would have seen it (Mitchell, n.d.), one might interpret hymns and subject them to theological, philosophical, moral, or “anagogical” lenses.

One can view, analyze, and interpret literature by means of other lenses. Purohit (2013) laid out M.H. Abrams’ approaches to literary criticism through his general classification of critical theories: (1) mimetic theories, (2) pragmatic theories, (3) expressive theories, and (4) objective theories. It has been posited by mimetic theories that literature can be viewed in light of what the artwork aims to represent or mimic. Pragmatic theories, on the other hand, Moreover, expressive theories focus on literature as a means for the author to convey his thoughts and expressions. Objective theories hold to the fact that literature is in itself a powerful source of analysis and interpretation. And certain literary critics, to understand a text deeply and deeper, would utilize several theories that would be compatible with each, depending on the need at hand and the level and quality of scrutiny. As such, literature connects itself with various disciplines in humanities and social sciences like history, sociology, philosophy, psychology, and others (Aras, 2015).

As such, literature can also be said as an utterance of expression of humanity. J.L. Austin introduced the speech act theory, wherein he divided speech acts into three parts: (1) locution, i.e. actual utterance (2) illocution, i.e. intention of the utterance and (3) perlocution, i.e. effect of the utterance by the speaker. Searle (1976) expounded the illocutionary acts into his own taxonomy: (1) representatives/assertives, where the speaker brings a truth of a statement; (2) directives, wherein the speaker gets to have the receiver to do something; (3) commissive, where the speaker commits himself to some future course of action; (4) expressive, wherein the

speaker gives out a psychological state of a condition or observed affairs; and (5) declarations, wherein the speaker alters a condition or status of the object/receiver. The study shall examine which illocutionary acts are present and how the utterances function in the selected hymns, in that these will serve as indicators for literariness and literary merit.

Research Questions

This study aims to examine the hymns “My Worth Is Not In What I Own” of the Gettys and Kendrick and “I’d Rather Have Jesus” of Miller on how elements drawn from the text would foreground man’s source of worth and identity. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What linguistic and literary features are highlighted and shared by both hymns?
2. Which illocutionary acts are present within the hymns?
3. How do these aesthetic features show negating/conflicting ideas within the hymns?
4. How do these aesthetic features and conflict uncover, reflect, and describe man’s source of worth and identity?

Literature Review

Gaps have been observed in studies examining human aspects like worth and identity, with respect to using certain literary theories. Sayuti (2020), in their discussion, stated that “literary phenomena is the whole of human experience which is sourced from the reality of life”, such that it shapes the identity of an individual and the society/culture he belongs in. Meena and Monika (2023) examined in their paper that literature shapes personality and changes behaviour, as in the case of the ancient Hindu Indian epic mythologies like Ramayana and Mahabharata (considered as traditional folk literature) through relating/empathizing with the character and referring back to the real human society and experience through education and the arts. Altun (2023) perceives identity (through literary characters) as “malleable” and “fluid”, in relation to real life-based characteristics and features. Altun further pointed out that through intersectionality, identity is highlighted through connection to social realities such as “interrelated elements that influence both their own identities and other people’s lives”. Stakić and Janković (2022) explored in their paper how literary texts influence the “forming and shaping of different layers of identity” through semantic structure using Ljubivoje Ršumović’s poetry. Ršumović’s pieces have been seen as “excellent for initiating conversations on different layers of identity, such as gender, sense of belonging” and the rest. The texts reviewed are then said to make pupils aware of their identity as means to develop and strengthen personality. Pachua and Lalrinfeli (2023) looked into how an individual’s identity is defined memory, and its power to shape identity and affect the self through Ishiguro’s selected works, such that one can “rewrite” oneself through memory and confirm one’s existence, rather than just telling the past. While their observations presented related ideas that literature serves as a key factor in the building of identity, few (if not none) studies have ventured into careful and deep stylistic and literary analysis to prove this.

While various literature have already been published with the subject of critiquing popular songs and various facets of its artistry, there are few studies endeavouring in the criticism of hymns. Within the analysis of hymns, several studies have been noted. Nnamdi-Eruchalu and Nwude (2022) employed a descriptive qualitative study in the analysis of the Searlean illocutionary acts in hymns. Using deliberate sampling, five hymns were subjected to scrutiny and findings proved that all of the five illocutionary acts are present in some parts of the five selected hymns and that these illocutionary acts serve different towards the ultimate goal of worshipping God and edifying the people. Bagayang (2022) underwent a similar pragmatic analysis on selected Christian hymns from the Catholic, Protestant, and Pentecostal denominations using the Austin-Searle framework. Discussion has pointed out that Protestant hymns have the highest expositive acts compared to the Catholic and Pentecostal hymns. Moreover, the findings also show the distinctives of each denomination: the Catholic hymns mention in frequency “the Holy Mass”, the Protestant hymns emphasize “God”, and the Pentecostal hymns stressed the person, power, and activities of the Holy Spirit. Wardani (2016) also utilized a descriptive qualitative design, but analysed the expressive utterances of the Psalms from the Old Testament. Investigating the syntactic nature of the expressive utterance of the Psalms, 30.48% are written in simple sentences, and in function, the same dataset also amounts to the highest percentage in terms of sentence function type (i.e. declaratives). Wardani’s expressive utterances are reported to have the main intention of praising God (54.9%). Ojo (2023) looked into Gospel Apala music, a variant of the popular African Apala music integrated as Christian worship in relation to systemic functional linguistics (SFL) and sociology of literature. The study employed a historical-descriptive qualitative research design. Thematic analysis showed that several themes emerged, including praise and thanksgiving to God, acknowledging Jesus as the essential need for salvation, and the greatness of God through His miracles. Stylistic analysis foregrounded the devices used to emphasize the point of the songs and those who sing it and sing of its message: repetition, use of rhetorical questions, personification, use of loan words, code-mixing/switching, and presence of proverbs. Furthermore, various literature regarding the employment of Searle’s illocutionary acts in the criticism of films and speeches have been also noted. However, application of these concepts in line with Formalist theories and in relation to the Searlean illocutionary acts has not yet been explored thoroughly in academic research.

Methodology

Research Design

This paper utilized the descriptive qualitative design. The descriptive design “answers exploratory qualitative questions that do not fit

into the framework of a more traditional design", where it has also been regarded as interpretive (National University California, 2023).

Participants

Using the purposive sampling technique, two sources of data have been utilized in this study, both of which are classified as Contemporary Christian hymns. The first hymn is “My Worth Is Not In What I Own”, written by Kristyn and Keith Getty and Graham Kendrick. The other hymn subjected to the analysis is “I’d Rather Have Jesus” written by Rhea F. Miller. These have been selected in that while chronologically, they have been recent additions to hymnaries in the 20th and 21st centuries and that structurally, these songs contain refrains, these contemporary hymns still are “structured and complex”(Chapman, 2023) and contain the personal experience retold through the lyrics. Repeated refrains have been included in the textual analysis.

Data Analysis

This study made use of both the hymns (1) document analysis and (2) thematic analysis, using close reading, stylistics, and Formalist and New Criticism theories of literary criticism. Bowen (2009) defined document analysis as a “systematic procedure” used to review and evaluate both printed and electronic documents. Furthermore, document analysis entails “finding, selecting, making sense of, and synthesizing data” in the utilized documents.

Thematic analysis is the “most appropriate for any study that seeks to discover using interpretations” (). This stems from the nature of qualitative research where diverse aspects of data are examined. Miles and Huberman (1994) laid out a three-link stages model for thematic analysis, which includes (1) data reduction, (2) data display, and (3) data conclusion-drawing/verifying.

Figure 1. Miles and Huberman (1994) Model of Thematic Analysis, in Alhojailan (2012)

Data reduction is the process of selecting, focusing on, and simplifying raw data collected; data display is making sense of the organized and compressed information, and data conclusion-drawing/verifying is where the researcher (as the main tool for analysis) interprets the data to draw conclusions or make assertions.

Results and Discussion

Linguistic Features Shared and Evident in the Two Hymns

Frequency of First-Person Pronouns

Both of the lyrics open with first-person pronouns. In the song “My Worth Is Not In What I Own”, the opening starts with the pronoun phrase “my”. The song “I’d Rather Have Jesus” is also opened by a first- person pronoun: I. The initial reference of the songs is the self, where identity is centered and to be established. This conformed to the usual grammatical syntax in referencing oneself.

Table 1. Frequency of First-Person Pronouns in the two Hymns

Hymns	My	I/I’d
“My Worth Is Not In What I Own”	14	10
“I’d Rather Have Jesus”	0	10
Total	14	20

The hymns would later present more references to the first person, where the first-person possessive (my) appeared lesser than the first-person subjective (I). This data is in agreement with Hussey (2019), who noted that first person singular pronouns are more evident among contemporary Christian songs than traditional hymns, the former being more "personal and individualistic" than the latter.

Semantics and Syntax and Implication of Quality of Certain Elements over One Person

Word choice and word use also leads to the unraveling of man and his worth and identity. In the song “My Worth Is Not In What I Own”, the first two lines of Verses 1 and 2 used negation for effect, in that there would be a shifting or conflicting to other ideas present in the hymn. These phrases denote mortality and limitations determined by the negation.

“...not in what I own

Not in the strength of flesh and bone”

”... not in skill or name

In win or lose, in pride or shame”

The first two lines of Verses 3 and 4 used direct statements to point to the ideas of mortality. “As summer flowers we fade and die

Fame, youth and beauty hurry by”

“I will not boast in wealth or might Or human wisdom’s fleeting light”

The last two lines of all the verses also show negation, but this negation gauges the line of thought of the source of worth and identity towards the positive. Consistent to every fourth line of the verses in the song “My Worth Is Not In What I Own” is the cross of Christ, where mortality of man is compared to a better means of worth and identity, through the death of Christ himself.

“But in the costly wounds of love At the cross”

“But in the blood of Christ that flowed At the cross”

“But I will boast in knowing Christ At the cross”

The refrain used a direct statement, emphasizing the source of worth and identity is in the superlative (greatest treasure, satisfaction, security, and pleasure), and is the cause of joy.

“I rejoice in my Redeemer Greatest Treasure, Wellspring of my soul

I will trust in Him, no other.

My soul is satisfied in Him alone.”

In the song “I’d Rather Have Jesus”, every verse in the lines is opened by “I’d rather”, a contraction of the words “I would” that denotes a notion of preference of one thing over another.

“I’d rather have Jesus than silver or gold; I’d rather be His than have riches untold; I’d rather have Jesus than houses or lands. I’d rather be led by His nail-pierced hand.”

“I’d rather have Jesus than men’s applause; I’d rather be faithful to His dear cause;

I’d rather have Jesus than worldwide fame. I’d rather be true to His holy name.”

Literary Features Shared and Evident in the Two Hymns

Use of Synecdoche as means to strengthen comparison

The songs utilized synecdoche to foreground comparison of certain elements within the lyrics. The hymn “My Worth Is Not in What I Own” highlights and shows this displaying of the parts of human existence and aspects that eventually leads these ideas into a bigger idea that human worth can be said to be “mortal”, “fading”, and “ceasing”.

“...the strength of flesh and bone” “... in skill or name”

“In win or lose, in pride or shame” “Fame, youth and beauty hurry by” “... in wealth or might”

“Or human wisdom’s fleeting light” “My worth and my unworthiness” “My value fixed – my ransom paid”

The hymn “I’d Rather Have Jesus” uses synecdoche to highlight the “material” and “worldly” elements of human life against the fulfilling worth and identity found in one person alone.

“... than silver or gold”

“... than have riches untold” ”... than houses or lands”

“Than to be the king of a vast domain...” “... than men’s applause”

“... than worldwide fame”

Rhyme in the Verses

Consistent form also was seen and shown to connote a stable and fixed source of worth and identity. In the hymn “My Worth Is Not in What I Own”, the rhymed lines are found as the first two lines of every quatrain/stanza.

“My worth is not in what I own (A)

Not in the strength of flesh and bone (A)”

”My worth is not in skill or name (B) In win or lose, in pride or shame (B)”

“As summer flowers we fade and die (C) Fame, youth and beauty hurry by (C)”

“I will not boast in wealth or might (D) Or human wisdom’s fleeting light (D)”

“Two wonders here that I confess (E) My worth and my unworthiness (E)”

In the hymn “I’d Rather Have Jesus”, the rhymed lines are evident within the quatrain. “I’d rather have Jesus than silver or gold; (A) I’d rather be His than have riches untold; (A) I’d rather have Jesus than houses or lands. (B) I’d rather be led by His nail-pierced hand.” (B)

“I’d rather have Jesus than men’s applause; (C) I’d rather be faithful to His dear cause; (C)

I’d rather have Jesus than worldwide fame. (D) I’d rather be true to His holy name.” (D)

Illocutionary Acts Shared and Evident in the Two Hymns

The Positive Assertion of Worth and Identity

Assertive act is the dominant illocutionary act for both songs. For the hymn “My Worth Is Not in What I Own”, the assertions tend to negate the materialistic person and instead defines the persona as the selfless and humbled person. Moreover, the assertive act reiterates that earthly pursuits are shadowed by identity formation and worth building through loftier spiritual pursuits.

Table 2. Evidence of Assertive Act in “My Worth Is Not in What I Own”

Lyric	Type of Illocutionary Act/Force
“My worth is not in what I own “Not in the strength of flesh and bone”	Assertive negation, asserting, claiming
“My worth is not in skill or name In win or lose, in pride or shame” "As summer flowers we fade and die" "Fame, youth and beauty hurry by"	asserting, claiming, stating a truth/reality
‘Two wonders here that I confess My worth and my unworthiness My value fixed – my ransom paid’	asserting, claiming, stating a truth/reality

For the hymn “I’d Rather Have Jesus”, the assertive illocutionary act proves to be the dominant illocutionary act throughout the hymn. As the use of the pronoun “my” is seen throughout the hymn, the tone of the speaker tells of longing and desire to connect and commune more deeper with Jesus.

Table 3. Evidence of Assertive Act in “I’d Rather Have Jesus”

Lyric	Type of Illocutionary Act/Force
“I’d rather have Jesus than silver or gold” “I’d rather be His than have riches untold” “I’d rather have Jesus than houses or lands” “I’d rather be led by His nail pierced hand” “Than to be the king of a vast domain or be held in sin’s dread sway” “I’d rather have Jesus than anything this world affords today” “I’d rather have Jesus than men’s applause” “I’d rather be faithful to His dear cause” "I’d rather have Jesus than worldwide fame" “I’d rather be true to His holy name”	Assertive Preference Comparison to a Greater Degree/Standard

Both hymns present powerful affirmations leading to self-worth and identity, challenging and contrasting conventional notions of value and offering a compelling alternative rooted in spiritual truths and in the Divine.

A Re-direction of Worth and Identity

The declarative act is another illocutionary act for both songs. For the hymn “My Worth Is Not in What I Own”, the speaker, having drawn to the positive assertion from the same lines, is compelled to have a change of mind, to reconsider their thoughts and values in their everyday life and their priorities both in the temporal and spiritual world. The hymn seeks to have its persona (and ultimately, its reader-listeners) alter their mindset through the re-direction of worth and identity that is outside of them and reassess their life's choices. As such, it is a re-direction and transformation of a pre-conceived identity and worth based on materialistic and temporal values, with the cross of Christ being a focal point in this redirection.

Table 4. Evidence of Declarative Act in “My Worth Is Not in What I Own”

Lyric	Type of Illocutionary Act/Force
"My worth is not in what I own Not in the strength of flesh and bone But in the costly wounds of love At the cross"	Declarative reference re-direction focal point
“My worth is not in skill or name In win or lose, in pride or shame But in the blood of Christ that flowed At the cross”	
“But life eternal calls to us At the cross”	
“Two wonders here that I confess My worth and my unworthiness My value fixed – my ransom paid at the cross”	

For the hymn “I’d Rather Have Jesus”, the declarative act is evident in that the speaker is led to the change of preference and priorities, as evidenced by the incipit "I'd rather have Jesus". Similarly to that of the first hymn, the redirection is an altering of the speaker's state of mind to reshape and reassess priorities of spiritual and higher pursuits and temporal-materialistic elements.

Table 5. Evidence of Declarative Act in “I’d Rather Have Jesus”

Lyric	Type of Illocutionary Act/Force
“I’d rather have Jesus than silver or gold”	Declarative Preference Comparison to a Greater Degree/Standard Referential
“I’d rather be His than have riches untold”	
“I’d rather have Jesus than houses or lands”	
“I’d rather be led by His nail pierced hand”	
“Than to be the king of a vast domain or be held in sin's dread sway”	
“I’d rather have Jesus than anything this world affords today”	
“I’d rather have Jesus than men's applause”	
“I’d rather be faithful to His dear cause”	
"I'd rather have Jesus than worldwide fame"	
“I’d rather be true to His holy name”	

Thus, both songs have the transformational power of language in shaping the identity and worth, underscoring the importance of both persuasion and direction for such transformation to be possible.

A Response to the Newfound Worth and Identity

Another illocutionary act observed and evident in the two songs is the expressive act. In the hymn “My Worth Is Not in What I Own”, satisfaction and humbled joy is the response of the persona in their rediscovery of one’s identity and worth, in that the Divine is the source of said aspects of humanity after introspection that led to humility and spiritual awakening. Moreover, the expressive act is evident in that the pleasure is beyond the material but in the Divine/Spiritual Treasure: Christ himself. This is most true in certain lines of the refrain.

Table 6. Evidence of Expressive Act in “My Worth Is Not in What I Own”

Lyric	Type of Illocutionary Act/Force
"I rejoice in my Redeemer" "My soul is satisfied in Him alone"	Expressive joy, satisfaction

Meanwhile, in the hymn “I’d Rather Have Jesus”, contentment in secure, everlasting, and pure source of this identity is greatly seen in the incipit/title, where it shows positive assertion, re-direction and shifting of purpose, preference/response to a Christ-based/rooted identity and worth. As such, the speaker speaks of a deep desire for spiritual contentment and fulfillment.

Table 7. Evidence of Expressive Act in “I’d Rather Have Jesus”

Lyric	Type of Illocutionary Act/Force
“I’d rather have Jesus than silver or gold”	Expressive Preference Contentment Better Value Better Condition
“I’d rather be His than have riches untold”	
“I’d rather have Jesus than houses or lands”	
“I’d rather be led by His nail pierced hand”	

<p>held in sin's dread sway”</p> <p>“I'd rather have Jesus than anything this world affords today”</p> <p>“I'd rather have Jesus than men's applause”</p> <p>“I'd rather be faithful to His dear cause”</p> <p>“I'd rather have Jesus than worldwide fame”</p> <p>“I'd rather be true to His holy name”</p>	<p>Comparison to a Greater Degree/Standard Referential</p>
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The interconnectedness of these illocutionary acts can be visualized in the figure below in that as one finds their worth and identity, it may lead towards affirmation of worth and identity, re-direction towards a better worth and identity, and a fitting reaction/reply to the newfound worth and identity.

Figure 2. A Chart on the Meaning-Making in Identity and Self-Worth based on the three evident Searlean illocutionary acts from the two hymns

Themes and Central Irony Shared by the Two Hymns

Switching of Reference in the First Lines

As stated above. However, the reference has been pointed away from the self, outside the self. It is evident in the incipit of the songs: My worth is not in what I own and I'd rather have Jesus. While the pronoun is in the first-person, the self is not fed something that would boost pride of oneself. Rather, the self is directed towards somewhere, something, and someone else higher and better than oneself.

Sense of Exclusivity, Totality, Primary Source towards the Only Source of One's Total Worth and Identity

The songs referred to self-denial of the material within the viewpoint of the persona, as reinforced by the previously observed and discovered details such as the literary feature of comparison and linguistic feature of negation, reinforced by several illocutionary acts that emphasize the meaning-making of identity and self-worth. As such, the highest standard of identity and self-worth is exclusive, in that it is only good for those who venture spiritual endeavours and find contentment in the divine as their supreme pleasure and treasure in this life and the next. Therefore, the primary source of identity and self-worth is also understood to be the only better source of one's identity and self-worth: Christ and the pursuit of His heavenly things.

Thus, the two songs would show worth outside of the self and negations found in the lyrics do not necessarily degrade, demean, or belittle the persona. Rather, identity and self-worth is denying oneself and acknowledging a power greater than oneself who is able to change their view identity and self-worth into His, and that pursuit of the One who gives an improved identity and self-worth is worth following than anything fleeting or earthly, as the Prophet Isaiah puts it: “His ways are better than ours”.

Conclusions

Hymns do not only express spiritual and theological truths. As this study has unraveled, hymns can also foreground aspects of humanity in relation to the Divine. The paper has brought to light linguistic evidences and literary devices that expounded, emphasized, and enlightened the persona, coupled with assertive, directive, and expressive acts of Searle that identity and worth anchored in earthly affinity is morally and spiritually poor but an identity and worth rooted in the Divine through knowing Him and pursuing His ways are more worth to life than anything else. And while this paper made use of objective critical theory by means of Formalism, the findings can be drawn to the Scriptural reference of Philippians 3:8, that “everything else is worthless when compared with the infinite value” of knowing Jesus that one will have “discarded everything else, counting it all as garbage” in order to “gain Christ”. The findings too can be connected to the doctrine of Christian Hedonism, coined by Baptist Pastor Dr. John Piper, summarized by the statement “God is most glorified in man when man is most satisfied in Him”. Literary analysis of lyrics and poetry allows humanity to see themselves in a more profound sense of worth and identity. This study then suggests and urges for similar endeavours of literary analysis in religious texts and hymnaries not only within Christendom, but may venture activities from other faiths as well.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jethro James V. Achivida, LPT
STI College – Philippines